

HadISDH Update Document

Date of Document Modification:

16th June 2016

Text to add to Dataset webpage:

The HadISDH.v2.1.0.2015p contains all 12 months of 2015, a minor code change to the homogenisation software and some historical changes to the data due to source archive changes. and minor changes to applied homogeneity adjustments due to sensitivity to both the historical changes and additional 12 months of data. More information can be found in the HadISDH.v2.1.0.2015p_Update_Document.pdf (LINK) and at <http://hadisdh.blogspot.co.uk/2016/06/2015-update-for-hadisdh2102015p.html>.

New Version Number vX.Y.Z.0000p/f:

v2.1.0.2015p

Major Changes X:

None

Minor Changes Y:

The PHA software used to homogenise the data has been updated to v52j. The main effect is to reduce over-sensitivity in data-sparse scenarios where changes in allocation of adjustments can occur due to small incremental additions of datapoints.

Bug fixes / historical data updates Z:

Retrospective improvements to the historical data in the ISD archive are ongoing and have been incorporated here. These have not been documented. The result on the gridded product is negligible but there is one fewer station than in the previous version and very slight differences in the final (passing through QC and homogenisation) source station list.

New Start Date DD.MM.YYYY:

No change

New End Date DD.MM.YYYY:

31.12.2015

New hadisdhTable:

No change – URL: <http://cedadocs.badc.rl.ac.uk/1267/>

New Reference:

No change

Any other notes to add:

None – could highlight the “For more detailed information e.g bug fixes, routine updates and other exploratory analysis, see the HadISDH blog: <http://hadisdh.blogspot.co.uk/>” in red or bold? The update blog post is here:

<http://hadisdh.blogspot.co.uk/2016/5/2015-update-for-hadisdh2102015p.html>